

PREVALENCE OF METABOLIC SYNDROME AMONG THE POPULATION IN SOME POLYCLINICS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION

Pulatova K.S.

Ablyatifov A.B.

Samarkand State Medical Institute, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10531980

Introduction. Arterial hypertension and associated obesity of various degrees is one of the most pressing problems of modern medicine, associated with leading an unhealthy lifestyle. The concept of "healthy lifestyle" includes a rational diet, maintaining a normal body weight, regular and age-appropriate physical activity, giving up alcohol and tobacco. In 1981, scientists suggested that cases of a combination of different metabolic disorders should be designated by the term "metabolic syndrome". In 1988 Professor G.Reaven, on the basis of his own observations and generalization of other studies, proposed the hypothesis that insulin resistance, abdominal obesity, arterial hypertension, atherogenic dyslipidemia, and coronary heart disease are manifestations of a pathological state, which he proposed to call "syndrome X". In 1989. D.Caplan introduced the term "fatal quartet": a combination of diabetes mellitus, obesity, arterial hypertension and coronary heart disease. Metabolic syndrome is understood as a combination of at least two of the five disorders [H.Arnese,1992]: -insulin resistance with reduced carbohydrate tolerance and hyperinsulinemia; -dyslipoproteinemia with hypertriglyceridemia and reduced high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; -Tendency to thrombosis and increased plasma levels of plasminogen activator inhibitor;-arterial hypertension against a background of increased sympathetic nervous system activity; -generalized obesity with increased secretion of free fatty acids into the portal vein. According to scientific research, the prevalence of obesity in Uzbekistan in the general population was 20.4%. In the female population 22.1%, in the male population 11.5%, i.e. twice as low. There was also conducted a study of the effect of obesity on the growth of type 2 diabetes and prediabetes in Uzbekistan: the frequency of obesity in the group with type 2 diabetes was 41.6% in the male population, and 38.5% in the female population, respectively. The frequency of obesity in the group with prediabetes was 37.06% in the female population, in the male population 32.3% respectively. In the study of the etiology of metabolic syndrome it is necessary to differentiate the causes of the most common factors, namely: genetic predisposition; irrational diet; sedentary lifestyle; hypertension; stress; overdose of insulin in the treatment of diabetes; hormonal disorders. Based on the results of numerous studies, the occurrence and progression of hypertension have been associated with premature mortality associated with hypertension and, especially, its association with ACS, target organs, as well as with adverse behavioral factors due to lifestyle, environment and genetic characteristics of a person, which determine the occurrence, progression and premature mortality from CVD.

Goal of the work. To assess the prevalence of metabolic syndrome (MS) among the population of the Samarkand region, as well as the frequency of associated clinical conditions among patients with arterial hypertension (AH).

Materials and methods . The material for this study was the results of a study from the unorganized male and female population living in the city of Samarkand for 2023. One random medical district in the city and the rural population was selected, serving from 1.5 to

2 thousand patients (range 19–64 years). When examining a city medical district, the sample size was 1600 people, of which 440 people were diagnosed with hypertension and obesity. 1200 people were selected from a rural medical district, of which 209 people were diagnosed with hypertension and obesity.

Depending on body mass index (BMI) values, all participants were divided into groups depending on the degree of obesity: I st - 20-24.9; II st - 25-29.9; III st - 30-34.9 kg/sq.m .

Results. As follows from the results, the presence of overweight - class I obesity among patients with hypertension living in the city was 41.6%, among the population of rural areas - 36.0%. Overweight - obesity degree II among people with hypertension living in the city was 40.2%, and among the population of rural areas - 27.8%. Overweight - grade III obesity among city residents was 12.3%, among rural residents - 7.1%. The studied persons with hypertension living in the city were not overweight, 6% and 5.0% of the population in rural areas suffering from hypertension were also not overweight, cardiovascular diseases , in particular coronary heart disease (CHD), are most often noted. The results data for the Samarkand region showed the presence of coronary artery disease in patients with hypertension among men living in the city was higher than among men living in rural areas - 18.3% and 11.0%, respectively ($p < 0.001$). A similar pattern was observed among the female population (16.0% and 12.4%; $p < 0.05$, respectively).

Important epidemiological indicators, along with the incidence and prevalence of hypertension, are: the level of awareness of patients with arterial hypertension about their disease and the level of control of hypertension.

Awareness of patients with hypertension about the presence of the disease among the urban population was 87.5%, among the rural population 56.6%.

Of no small importance is the assessment of cardiovascular risk factors, which determines the prognosis of patients. In the Samarkand region, the most common risk factor in patients with hypertension was obesity ($BMI \geq 30$). Among men and women of the urban population, obesity was higher compared to men and women of the rural population - 17.2% and 11.7%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). Other risk factors include smoking, a sedentary lifestyle and alcohol consumption in part of the population being surveyed.

Conclusion. The results obtained can be used to plan and implement preventive programs aimed at reducing morbidity and mortality from IHD and diabetes mellitus, as well as promoting the health of the region under study. A timely assessment of the epidemiological situation with analysis of the causes development of diseases and associated comorbid conditions should lead to a significant reduction in the risk of cardiovascular complications.

References:

1. Abdulloyeva M., Pulatova K., Mirzaev R. ORTIQCHA VAZN VA ARTERIAL GIPERTONIYA BILAN OG'RIGAN YOSHLARDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN JINSIY ZAIFLIK //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2023. – T. 3. – No. 4 Part 2. – pp. 91-94.
2. Pulatova K. S. INFLUENCE OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS ON INSULIN RESISTANCE AND LIPID SPECTRUM INDICATORS // European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development . – 2023. – T. 15. – P. 72-75.

3. Dilshodovna AM, Odylovna KF, Samveilovna PK Peculiarities of Psychological Disorders in Patients with Acute Coronary Syndrome //International Journal of Health Systems and Medical Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – No. 6. – pp. 203-207.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY